

Leveraging Tourism: The Business of Timeshare

SUKARN SHARMA* and NIMIT CHOWDHARY**

*Sukarn Sharma, Ph.D. Asst. Professor, Manav Bharti University, Solan, (H.P) INDIA

**Nimit Chowdhary, Ph.D. Professor, Indian Institute of Tourism & Travel Management, Gwalior, (M.P) INDIA

ABSTRACT

Timeshare is one of the fastest-growing segments of the travel and tourism industry worldwide and it has grown over the decades to include a wide variety of vacation products and plans. It is a unique but a complex product which has earned billions for countries; however, in a few cases the application of the timeshare model was not very effective. With the consumer satisfaction index reaching a high of 85% and the number of companies and memberships being small, there arises a need for evaluating the prospects and concerns of timeshare industry in India so that a way towards success can be paved for the upcoming and existing timeshare companies. Therefore, to understand what should or should not be done interviews of the members of three different timeshare companies were undertaken, out of which one company was from public sector and two were from private sector. It was found that customers are not much concerned with the sale price, however the area where companies whether government or private should pay special attention is number of destinations.

Keywords: *Tourism accommodation, Timeshare, Condominiums, Fractional ownership, Second homes, Multi-ownership*

Introduction

Tourism has become an important business to which increasing attention is being paid by both public and private sectors, and the resources necessary for its development are being increasingly channeled. Tourism has come to be considered not merely as an economic phenomenon but as a powerful force for dialogue and understanding between different societies and cultures (WTO, 1997). Timeshare is one of the fastest-growing segments of the travel and tourism industry worldwide and it has grown over the

decades to include a wide variety of vacation products and plans (ATHOC, 2008). It has sustained double-digit growth since its inception (Hahm et al, 2007).

According to Oxford Dictionary timeshare is defined as “*an arrangement whereby joint owners use a property as a holiday home at different specified times*” (Askoxford.com, 2009). As per Timeshare consumers’ association timeshare is defined as “*form of holiday ownership. One owns the right (either directly or through a “club”) to use a week (or longer) in an apartment or villa on a holiday resort for a great many years or in perpetuity*” (TCA, 2005).

The first timeshare plan was introduced in the US in 1968, with the conversion of a hotel in Hawaii, but not much was really heard of timeshare there until the short-term collapse of the whole-ownership condominium sector in 1974. During the oil crisis in the mid-1970s, coming after a building boom in Florida, the idea of timeshare was adopted as the answer to the fall in the property market. Lowering the prices of units by converting them into weekly intervals meant that more people could afford them. Some uncertain condominium projects in St. Thomas, Fort Lauderdale and Puerto Rico were converted into timeshare projects but, in their desperate haste to make a sale, many of the projects failed due to poor legal structuring, financing and marketing. Nevertheless, although at this point timeshare projects were on a small scale, fragmented and relatively unregulated, timeshare had started to take off and by the end of the 1970s annual sales had risen to \$50 million (India Report, 2009).

Timeshare has evolved over the years from the fixed week system to the latest points system though all the systems have their own pros and cons. One of the biggest attractions of timesharing is the ability to exchange one’s timeshare week for a week at a different timeshare (Nelson, 2000).

The Timeshare product is complex and there are many components that are important for it to be successful, mainly the cooperation between Developer, the Marketing Company, the Exchange Company and Trustee (Revelas and Lagiewski, 2005). Many operators have chosen to develop timeshare alongside traditional hotel or other holiday accommodation developments. These projects have been referred to as ‘mixed use’ resorts and this has already proved to be a winning formula in other markets, especially the United States (European timeshare study, 2001). High satisfaction rates, affordability, and low market penetration hold the promise for future industry growth (Resort timesharing worldwide, 2003).

Review of literature

The WTO (1997) has stated that there are mounting evidences to show that timeshare has a positive impact on development areas. The financial benefits from timeshare include sales of timeshare, maintenance fees, local taxes, on-site payroll, and the purchase of travel facilities. A timeshare development creates permanent full time and part time jobs on site, and temporary jobs are created within the community. The conversion of hotel units to timeshare can release capital for much needed renovation in older hotels, and boost revenues in the short time. The timeshare phenomenon has a fundamental advantage for a tourism destination compared to the rest of the industry. While other types of tourism products have to be promoted anew each year, in timeshare the opposite is true. Once the timeshare user has bought his weeks, he is an identified user of travel services and is likely to be a good prospect for further timeshare sales. He is a guaranteed repeat client – and if he does not come, another owner and family will more than likely arrive, thanks to the exchange system. Negative feelings about timeshare arise from the selling practices of some companies, but are then attributed erroneously to the product itself.

A timeshare shouldn't be purchased-or sold-as an investment; it's a lifestyle buy for consumers (Watkins, 2007). Two divergent factors combine to drive the popularity of timeshares ownership among hotel owners. First, while the hotel operations earn revenues largely from hotel room charges, timeshare resorts have multiple sources, which include timeshare contract sales, interest payments on mortgaged suites, maintenance fees and club membership fees. Secondly, timeshares tend to be immune to variations in economic performance because the timeshare owners are contractually bound to occupy their units. From the consumer perspective, timeshares are not suitable for investment property because the expensive marketing programmes inflate the prices. The high marketing expenses force the property value to depreciate considerably over a short period. Even with this problem, surveys suggest that the owners are generally satisfied. Consumers should not enter into timeshare contracts, however, for investment purposes but for buying a vacation in advance (Powanga and Powanga, 2008).

The future growth within the timeshare industry is likely to emanate from three factors i.e. the emergence of new types of timeshare products such as the point system, the emergence of new markets for the timeshare

product and the expansion of existing timeshare markets (WTO, 1997). Bornstein (2002) cited that in an interview with John Burlingame in 2002 he stated that "Timeshare development is an incredibly profitable business which generates profits ranging between three to five times normal profits from a regular real estate sale". The resort timeshare industry has been built on the compelling commercial argument that the inherent profit from the realisation of the future value of the asset can be brought forward in time and recognised on the date of sale (WTO, 2005).

The prevailing wisdom is that while not recession-proof, timesharing is better able to weather the ups and downs of economic cycles than other segments of the hospitality industry. Unlike the rest of the hospitality industry, which took a nosedive in the months following 9/11, vacation ownership sales continued to grow at a double-digit annual pace (Watkins, 2008). With regard to the purchase decision the industry survey in 1998 found that the most important reasons for purchasing timeshare included flexibility, saving money, liking the resort and certainty of quality accommodation (Crotts and Ragatz, 2002).

The Indian scenario

In India, the concept arrived quite late and wholesomely welcomed since it meant buying future vacations at today's price. There exists a tremendous potential for timesharing in the Indian market and only 0.069% of the market are members (Destination Resorts India Pvt. Ltd., 2004). The timeshare industry is growing manifold with big brands such as Resort Condominiums International (RCI), Ramada Hotels & Resorts, Club Mahindra, Hyatt Vacation Club, etc. entering the business. Much of it still remains untapped and developers keep coming up with new, innovative and attractive deals (Sandhya and Unnikrishnan, 2009). India and China are expected to be potential targets of vacation ownership developers in the long-term (Official Wire 2009). The market for timeshare models in India is huge, and more importantly, domestic traffic is adopting a lifestyle that supports the timeshare model (Bhar, 2007).

The timeshare concept in India was introduced by Dalmia resorts in 1985 (Dalmia resorts, 2007) after which Sterling resorts were fast to catch up which came in to existence in 1986. During the years following incorporation, Sterling has built a network of 14 resorts in 12 holiday destinations in India and is having a membership base of over 100,000

Vacation Ownership members. In addition, the resorts in the Sterling network also offer vacationers in India, the option of staying as a one-time hotel guest (Sterling resorts, 2011). In today's date one of the major players in timeshare industry in India is Club Mahindra which has over the years evolved a position for itself and as of May 31, 2009, the Company was having 19 branches and 61 retail outlets across India of which 45 are owned and 16 are franchised. The company was also able to sell 91,997 Club Mahindra Holiday vacation ownership memberships. The company was incorporated in September, 1996 in Chennai as Mahindra Holidays & Resorts India Private Limited. The status of Company was changed to a public limited Company by a special resolution of the members passed at a shareholders' meeting held on January 29, 1998. The company is having 11 owned resorts and 16 resorts have been leased. Of the total 1,261 apartments and cottages offered 937 are owned, 252 are on long term leases and 72 are on short term leases (Club Mahindra, 2009).

According to India Report (2009) impact of branded hospitality players and reputed conglomerates is the need of the hour. Potential consumers, while agreeing to the benefits of the product, have often cited the lack of branded players as their reason for not purchasing timeshare, thus indicating a requirement for both credibility and glamour in the product. Further the report indicates that the demand for timeshare products in India is likely to grow at about 16 per cent annually from 2006 to 2015, facilitated by supply growth of about 12 per cent annually over the same period. This is reflected by the growth in holiday exchange bookings that increased by 28 per cent in January-November 2008. The average unit sale for a typical timeshare development is likely to grow at 3 per cent annually from 2006 to 2015. The average unit cost per day for a consumer is likely to grow at 4 per cent annually during the same period compared to 5-8 per cent for a pure hotel product. Every business has its success and failure stories and timeshare is no exception. From the time this concept was introduced in India, a lot of companies have entered this segment out of which most have been successful and a few unsuccessful. Timeshare schemes are being run by both Public and Private sector companies in India. Statistics from the latest survey of the timeshare industry confirm that the consumer satisfaction index is reaching a high of 85%. There are 40 timeshare companies, 80 resorts, 200,000 memberships with 15,000 annual additions and 4000 units. The average age of timeshare consumer is 42 years out of which 89.8% are

males having an average household size of 4 people with a typical children count of 1 to 2 children (AIRDA, 2008).

Importance Performance analysis

Systematic approach to mapping customer expectations helps managers to know better what aspects of a service best define its quality and can prepare the organization to take up a competitive position based upon its ability to deliver what customers demand (Cronin & Taylor, 1992). A direct measurement technique is the Importance-Performance analysis (IPA) technique which emerged from the earlier work of Martilla and James (1977). Unlike SERVPERF, the Importance- Performance technique allows simultaneous comparison of direct performance measure of service quality to the importance rating given by customers for the various quality items being evaluated. The inclusion of customer preference rating in IPA gives a better picture of customers' quality assessment of service. According to (Barsky, 1995) such relative assessments pinpoint clearly the quality aspects of product or service which contributes greatly to customer satisfaction. As a result the information derived out of importance-performance analysis (IPA) can aid the development of more focused marketing strategies (Ford, Joseph, & Joseph, 1999). This view is confirmed (Lovelock, Patterson & Walker, 1999) who state that importance-performance analysis is a useful management tool which can help firms to redirect their scarce resources from low impact areas to high impact areas. This technique is also called Key Driver Analysis. The importance-performance scale is based on the assumption that satisfaction is affected by both the importance of an attribute and perceived performance on the attribute. Designed for ease of transferring results into actions, the scale's end result is a graph indicating appropriate levels of action. A variant of importance performance analysis i.e. Expectation Experience Matrix (EEM) was used for this study. In EEM, customers' expectations and experiences have been plotted on a grid that is divided into 4 quadrants, formed based on the mean scores of the expectations-experience ratings. The variables are then assessed according to its position in the quadrant on the grid. Each quadrant suggests different response from a strategy point of view.

Variables that are rated high in expectation and high in experience (Quadrant 1) score suggest that service providers keep up the 'good' work and increase resources directed towards these areas. In contrast, variables

having low expectation rating and a low experience (Quadrant 3) rating suggest that investing resources to these areas may offer only little advantage and should therefore be on a lower priority. Variables that are rated high in expectation and low in experience (Quadrant 2) are the missed opportunities and service providers need to concentrate here and pay particular attention for improvement. Lastly, attributes rated low in expectations and high in experience (Quadrant 4) are areas of possible over kill. Providers should reconsider the level of effort. The beauty of EEM is that it can help a business understand what its customers feel is important to it across a number of relevant variables.

Research methodology

For the success of upcoming and existing timeshare companies there arises a need for evaluating the challenges and opportunities of timeshare industry in India as the number of companies and memberships are small. Therefore, for the research it was decided to administer a schedule on a sample of 53 respondents from the private timeshare companies (Club Mahindra and Country Club India) and 28 respondents from public timeshare company (HPTDC) who were chosen randomly from the customer base of their respective companies. The 28 respondents chosen randomly from HPTDC (Himachal Pradesh Tourism Development Corporation) were due to the reason as HPTDC was only able to sell 139 timeshare memberships during the period that it operated its timeshare scheme i.e. from 5th November, 1998 to 10th November, 1999. Therefore, a sample of 20% was thought to be a good representation of the whole population. Similarly 53 respondents from the private sector timeshare company were randomly chosen so as to equate with the number of respondents of HPTDC.

A feedback of these customers had been taken to understand the pluses and minuses of the timeshare companies whether it is a public or a private company. However the customers' list was not accessible due to privacy issues posed by timeshare companies hence, the customers were taken from communities on the social networking websites such as Orkut. List of customers has also been taken from websites which are reselling timeshares (Quickr and Ebay) due to which the number of respondents was limited. To have an analysis of the various responses given by the customers a variant of importance performance analysis i.e. Expectation Experience Matrix was used which is a standard analysis tool in tourism research. This matrix was used because it was thought that it is essential to segregate the variables

which are of utmost importance to the customers and on which the timeshare companies are not performing very well so that immediate attention can be paid to them by the timeshare industry.

Findings

Customers' experience rating and the expectation rating mean values for the eighteen variables used as input for the expectation experience matrix are presented in Table 1 and 2. These variables were chosen for the study because they were suggested by a panel of experts which comprised of professionals from the tourism and timeshare industry.

Table 1 : Expectation Experience Means (Private Sector Timeshare Company)

	Attributes	Mean Expectation (Y)	Mean Experience (X)
1	Sale price of timeshare	4.01	2.67
2	Lump sum/Amount of EMI	3.88	2.69
3	Number of destination	4.39	2.60
4	Overall condition of the resort	4.71	4.05
5	Location of the resort	4.67	4.07
6	Access to the resort	4.47	3.88
7	Room furnishing	4.73	4.01
8	View from the room	4.57	3.76
9	Food	4.76	4.01
10	Waiting time for billing	2.84	4.33
11	Competence of the sales staff	4.67	3.60
12	Competence of the front office staff	4.56	3.92
13	Competence of the housekeeping staff	4.67	4.35
14	Competence of the service staff	4.62	4.21
15	Tenure of ownership	4.15	3.16
16	Annual maintenance charges	4.64	2.05
17	Cancellation policy	2.60	2.11
18	Convenience in buying timeshare	4.37	4.56
	Total sum	77.31/18	61.36/18
	Grand Mean	4.29	3.40

As part of assessing timeshare attractiveness, these mean scores were plotted in an expectation experience matrix (normal scale) as shown in

figure 3. The grand means for experience rating ($x = 3.40$) and expectation ($y = 4.29$) determines the placements of axes on the grid.

Figure 1: Expectation Experience Matrix (Private Sector Timeshare Company)

Even though when the customers are quite happy with the quality of timeshare resorts that they are offered still they feel that the number of destinations (resorts) is quite less and they do not get much on their platter. However this problem can be overcome by having affiliation with an exchange company such as RCI, II, Dial an exchange, etc. Having an affiliation from an exchange company is also crucial because practically it is not

feasible for any of the timeshare companies to offer a bunch of resorts to the customers. Moreover having an affiliation also opens the international gateway for the customers. The second issue is of annual maintenance charges which customers feel are quite high. This issue can be tackled if companies start charging a lump sum amount which consists of the membership fee as well as the annual maintenance charges right away at the time when a member gets enrolled. This can also be done considering customers have rated sale price as low in expectation and low in experience. *(However the reason for sale price to be low in experience might be that the customers would have thought if they will rate it otherwise there may not be a hike in the future)*. Moreover by charging the annual maintenance fee initially a customer will at least psychologically feel that he has paid the entire amount and now it is his time to relax. This also helps the company in two ways first, the company is assured that the whole amount of money is with them and there is no chance of customer defaulting at a later stage. Second, company is able to get more cash as compared to charging sale price initially and then charging annual maintenance charges later on. Still being in this quadrant these are areas where most attention is needed to turn them into areas of strength (quadrant 2).

The variables which fall in quadrant 3 are sale price, lump sum/amount of EMI, cancellation policy and tenure of ownership. The possible reason for the first two factors to be rated low in expectation is because financially these factors are not a burden for the customers but on the contrary customers have also avoided to rate them high in experience thinking that there might not be a hike in the future. However, being in this quadrant these variables clearly indicate that these areas are less important and customers are more concerned with other areas of the timeshare scheme. It was also felt that customers make their buying decisions regarding timeshare after a careful thought and that is why they have rated cancellation policy in this quadrant. Tenure of ownership is also in this quadrant which indicates that people are satisfied with their timeshare scheme and therefore, want the tenure to be increased. However a low expectation for this attribute also signals that people give weightage to other things even if the tenure is not enough.

The probable reason for waiting time for billing (only item in quadrant 4) to be rated in this quadrant can be, that people are used to this level of service and do not see anything extraordinary.

For the segment that private timeshare companies are serving, competitive advantage emerges out of overall condition, access & location of the resort, room furnishing, food, competence of the staff, view from the room and convenience in buying timeshare (items in quadrant 1). There appears to be a potential in targeting the growing Indian middle class as the trend now is towards more fun filled holidays rather than Visiting Friends and Relatives (VFR).

Note: * 1 respondent has not given any response regarding room furnishing, view from the room and food.

* 2 respondents have not given any response regarding billing and competence of service staff.

* 19 respondents have said that they have never thought about cancelling their membership. It is not important for them and they have never asked for it.

Table 2 : Expectation Experience Means (Public Sector Timeshare Company)

	Attributes	Mean Expectation (Y)	Mean Experience (X)
1	Sale price of timeshare	3.85	3.28
2	Lump sum/Amount of EMI	3.10	3.10
3	Number of destination	4.82	3.00
4	Overall condition of the resort	4.85	3.50
5	Location of the resort	4.92	4.25
6	Access to the resort	4.92	4.46
7	Room furnishing	4.75	3.42
8	View from the room	4.92	4.57
9	Food	4.67	4.14

	Attributes	Mean Expectation (Y)	Mean Experience (X)
10	Waiting time for billing	2.67	4.00
11	Competence of the sales staff	4.64	4.32
12	Competence of the front office staff	4.82	4.14
13	Competence of the housekeeping staff	4.75	3.96
14	Competence of the service staff	4.64	3.96
15	Tenure of ownership	4.67	3.67
16	Annual maintenance charges	3.75	3.03
17	Cancellation policy	3.60	4.35
18	Convenience in buying timeshare	4.32	4.57
	Total sum	78.66	69.72
		78.66/18	69.72/18
	Grand Mean	4.37	3.87

As part of assessing timeshare attractiveness, these mean scores were plotted in an expectation experience matrix (normal scale) as shown in figure 4. The grand means for experience rating ($x = 3.87$) and expectation ($y = 4.37$) determines the placements of axes on the grid.

Figure 2 : Expectation Experience Matrix (Public Sector Timeshare Company)

The timeshare customers of Public Sector Company feels that overall condition of the resort, number of destination, room furnishing and tenure of ownership are major areas of concern. The company may improve the condition of its resorts and furnishing of its rooms as timeshare owners are the persons who will not come to the resort only once but they are the people who are going to visit the resorts year after year and that too at least for a week's time in one go. The company was only having a few properties in its timeshare scheme which are quite less as compared to any other timeshare company which offers hundreds of properties. This is only

possible because every timeshare company has a tie up with an exchange company that can be with RCI, II, Dial an Exchange, etc. The company can improve on the number of resorts by having affiliations with exchange companies and it can also consider involving all its properties in the timeshare scheme. Moreover having an affiliation also opens the international gateway for the customers. Whereas the tenure of ownership is concerned it is a positive signal for the company which indicates that people are satisfied and that is why they want the tenure to be increased. Still being in this quadrant these are areas where most attention is needed to turn them into areas of strength (quadrant 2). The variables which fall in quadrant 3 are sale price, lump sum/amount of EMI and annual maintenance charges. At the first sight it appears more contradictory as the low sale price and annual maintenance fee could have been more of a satisfier. However, the possible reason for these attributes to be rated low in importance is because financially these factors were not a burden for the customers but on the contrary customers have also avoided to rate them high in performance thinking that there might not be a hike in the future. The attributes in quadrant 4 are convenience in buying timeshare, cancellation policy and waiting time for billing. As these factors are not treated very important by the customers therefore, the company should continue to maintain these services at the same level only. Nevertheless there are customers who perceive these attributes very important and would definitely want these factors to be there in the scheme. The competitive advantage emerges out of the view from the room, access to the resort, location of the resort, competence of the staff and food (items in quadrant 1). Therefore there appears to be a potential if the company can effectively create a sales package of its resorts, food and its hospitable staff.

*Note: * Food - 1 respondent has not given his response for the quality of food.*

Conclusion

Timeshare is a successful business venture around the world. However there are ups and downs in every business. If one looks at the internet one will find complaints of almost every company, whether it is banking, insurance, telecom or any other sector. The similar story is with timeshare also but reports from organizations of repute such as AIRDA, ARDA etc. has proved that most of the customers are satisfied with their timeshare scheme.

Table 3 : Comparison of Public and Private Sector Timeshare Company

Quadrant	Public sector company	Private sector company
Quadrant 2	overall condition of the resort, number of destination, room furnishing and tenure of ownership	number of destinations, annual maintenance charges
Quadrant 3	sale price, lump sum/amount of EMI and annual maintenance charges	sale price, lump sum/amount of EMI, cancellation policy and tenure of ownership
Quadrant 4	convenience in buying timeshare, cancellation policy and waiting time for billing	waiting time for billing
Quadrant 1	view from the room, access to the resort, location of the resort, competence of the staff and food	overall condition, access & location of the resort, room furnishing, food, competence of the staff, view from the room and convenience in buying timeshare

As can be seen from table 3 above number of destinations is an area of concern whether the company is in public sector or private sector. The only possible way out of this problem is to increase the number of self owned resorts and to have tie ups with exchange companies. *(It should be kept in mind that private companies are already having tie ups with exchange companies)*. It may be of interest to note that in case of private company the annual maintenance charges are of concern but customers are happy with other things whereas in case of public company customers are more concerned with overall condition of the resort, room furnishing and tenure of ownership. This shows that upkeep of the resort comes at a cost and customers may have to bear on either side i.e. in terms of annual maintenance charges or in terms of condition of the resort.

Both sale price and lump sum/amount of EMI are rated as low in expectation and low in experience by the customers of public and private sector companies which indicate that customers are more concerned with other facilities that they get at the resorts. However, the possible reason for these attributes to be rated low in expectation is because financially these factors were not a burden for the customers but on the contrary customers

have also avoided to rate them high in experience thinking that there might not be a hike in the future. The competitive advantage of private and public sector companies emerges out of view from the room, access to the resort, location of the resort, competence of the staff and food. Therefore, these factors can make an effective sales package. In the future studies may be carried on the scope of fractional ownership in India and on feasibility of newer products like destination clubs in Indian scenario. Fractional ownership has already been launched in India by Country Club India ltd.

REFERENCES

- AIRDA (All India Resort Development Association) (2008), (Online) (Retrieved 30th August, 2008) Available from URL www.airda.org
- ATHOC (Australian Timeshare and Holiday Ownership Council Limited (2008) (Online) (Retrieved 06th August, 2009) Available from URL http://www.athoc.com.au/files/consumer_guide/athoc_consumerguide_lowres.pdf
- Barsky, J. D. (1995). *World-class customer satisfaction*. Burr Ridge, Illinois: Irwin Professional Pub.
- Bhar Sanjeev, Timeshare concept will boost resort development in India, (Online) (1-15 November 2007) (Retrieved 23rd November, 2008) Available from URL <http://www.expresshospitality.com/20071115/market08.shtml>
- Bornstein S. Ethan, The future of the timeshare Industry: Will the brands dominate? A summary of the vacation ownership industry and an analysis of the advantages that the brands have over smaller independent developers, Master's thesis, (Online), September, 2002, (Retrieved 2nd August, 2009) Available from URL <http://dspace.mit.edu/bitstream/handle/1721.1/32225/51886529.pdf?sequence=1>
- Club Mahindra, (2009) (Online) (Retrieved 12th August, 2009) Available from URL www.clubmahindra.com
- Cronin, J. J., & Taylor, S. S. (1992). Measuring service quality: A reexamination and extension. *Journal of Marketing*, 56, 55-68.
- Crotts, John C., and Ragatz L. Richard 2002. Recent U.S. timeshare purchasers: Who are they, what are they buying, and how can they be reached? *Hospitality Management* 21:227-38.
- Dalmia Resorts (2007) (Online) (Retrieved 17th April, 2011) Available from URL http://www.dalmiaresorts.com/about_us.html
- Destination Resorts India Pvt. Ltd. (2004) (Online) (Retrieved 14th March,

- 2008) Available from URL <http://www.driindia.com/historytimeshare.html>
- European timeshare Industry in 2001: OTE Study (Online) (Retrieved 29th November, 2008) Available from URL <http://www.rdo.org/node/22>
- Evans, M. R., & Chon, K. S. (1989). Formulating and evaluating tourism policy using importance-performance analysis. *Hospitality Education and Research Journal*, 13, 203-2-13.
- Ford, J. B., Joseph, M., & Joseph, B. (1999). IPA as a strategic tool for service marketers: The case of service quality perceptions of business students in New Zealand and the USA. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 13 (2), 171-186.
- Hahm Jeeyeon, Lasten Earney, Upchurch S Randall, Peterson Ryan, State of timeshare industry in Aruba – A call for research, *Journal of Retail & Leisure Property*. London: Jul 2007. Vol. 6, Iss. 3, p. 221-229 (9 pp.) (Online) (Retrieved 09th August, 2009) Available from URL <http://proquest.umi.com/pqdweb?did=1336836681&Fmt=3&clientId=43456&RQT=309&VName=PQD>
- Hemmasi, M., Strong, K. C., & Taylor, S. A. (1994). Measuring service quality for strategies planning and analysis in service firms. *Journal of Applied Business Research*, 10 (4), 24-34
- India Report, The Spectrum of Leisure Real Products in India, A Cushman & Wakefield and Group RCI Publication, (January, 2009), (Online) (Retrieved 17th September, 2009) Available from URL www.sapphirez.co.in/.../The_spectrum_of_Leisure_real_estate_products_in_India.28170022.pdf
- Keyt, J. C., Yavas, U., & Riecken, G. (1994). Importance- performance analysis: A case study in restaurant positioning. *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*, 22 (5), 35-40.
- Martin, D. W. (1995). An importance-performance analysis of service providers' perception of quality service in the hotel industry. *Journal of Hospitality & Leisure Marketing*, 3 (1), 5-17.
- Lovelock, C., Patterson, P. G., & Walker, R. H. (1999). *Services Marketing*. Sydney: Prentice Hall.
- Martilla, J., & James, J. (1977). Importance- performance analysis. *Journal of Marketing*, 1, 77-79.
- Nelson J. Stephen, Timesharing 101 - A TUG Introduction to Timesharing, (November, 2000) (Online) (Retrieved 11th September, 2009) Available from URL <http://www.tug2.net/advice/TimeShare-101.htm>
- Official Wire, "Wyndham is the largest vacation ownership operator by number of properties, owners, units and revenues" (2009) (Online) (Retrieved 2nd September, 2009) Available from URL http://www.officialwire.com/main.php?action=posted_news&rid=14383&catid=679

- Powanga Atupele & Powanga Luka, School of Management, Regis University, USA, (2008), An economic analysis of a timeshare ownership, *Journal of Retail and Leisure Property*, (online) (Retrieved 23rd November, 2008) Available from URL <http://www.palgrave-journals.com/rlp/journal/v7/n1/full/5100082a.html>
- Resort Timesharing Worldwide, (2003) (Online) (Retrieved 05th-August, 2009) Available from URL http://www.rci.com/CDA/HTML/PDF_Conversion_Files/Worldwide_Timeshare_Summary_Mar_31_03.pdf
- Revelas A. Damon & Lagiewski M. Richard "Rick", *Timeshare as a strategy in Tourism investment: The case of Croatia (2005)* (Online) (Retrieved 05th August, 2009) Available from URL <https://ritdml.rit.edu/dspace/bitstream/1850/1602/1/RLagiewskiConfProc10-2005.pdf>
- Sandhya. P and Unnikrishnan Namrata, "Timeshare or Timescare", *Indlawnews.com* (2009) (online) (Retrieved 10th January, 2009) Available from URL <http://www.indlawnews.com/display.aspx?2806>
- Sterling Holidays (2011) (Online) (Retrieved 17th April, 2011) Available from URL <http://www.sterlingholidays.in/about-us/overview.aspx>
- Watkins E.D., *Timeshare tests a theory*, *Lodging Hospitality*. Cleveland: Apr 15, 2008. Vol. 64, Iss. 5; pg. 42, 2 pgs, (Online) (Retrieved 10th August, 2009) Available from URL <http://proquest.umi.com/pqdweb?did=1475946611&Fmt=3&clientId=43456&RQT=309&VName=PQD>
- Watkins E.D., *Time to rethink timesharing*, *Lodging Hospitality*, Cleveland: Oct 2007. Vol. 63, Iss. 15; pg. 4, 1 pgs, (Online), (Retrieved 09th August, 2009) Available from URL <http://proquest.umi.com/pqdweb?did=1370459781&Fmt=3&clientId=43456&RQT=309&VName=PQD>
- WTO (World Tourism Organisation), *Timeshare-The new force in Tourism* (1997), (Online) (Retrieved 19th August, 2009) Available from URL [http://www.wtoelibrary.org/content/?k=ti%3a\(Timeshare+The+new+force+in+Tourism+\)&sortorder=asc](http://www.wtoelibrary.org/content/?k=ti%3a(Timeshare+The+new+force+in+Tourism+)&sortorder=asc)
- WTO (World Tourism Organisation), *Tourism Statistics and measurement of Timeshare comments on world Tourism Organisation Discussion Paper, Tourism statistics and the measurement of timeshare, (20th to 24th June, 2005)* (Online) (Retrieved 07th January, 2008) Available from URL <http://209.85.175.104/search?q=cache:R4r3bQROVYoj:unstats.un.org/unsd/class\intercop/expertgroup/2005/AC103BK5.PDF+benefits+hotels+can+derive+by+selling+timeshares&hl=en&ct=clnk&cd=7&gl=in>